

June 30, 2025

<https://ijoabs.com/>
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

Producer Support and Supervision Systems, a Fragile Crutch in the Service of Family Farming In Eastern Cameroon

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Received Date: 30-March-2025

Accepted Date: 30-May-2025

Published Date: 15-June-2025

Abstract

Rural agriculture is very important for developing countries. Indeed, depending on the importance given to rural areas in public policies, it can either promote growth or even development, or hinder it. Agriculture is the common thread of rural development, which itself relies on family farms. Rural development is, in principle, a process that comprehensively aims to improve the living and working conditions of rural populations. As a result, agriculture, as the driving force of the rural economy, remains the pillar of policies for the emergence of rural development. This places systems of supervision and support for agricultural producers at the heart of socioeconomic dynamics and at the center of their implementation on family agropastoral farms. However, by struggling to be deployed on the ground, they weaken family farming.

Keywords: Rural development, supervision and support of producers, family agropastoral farms, farmers' organization, agriculture

Introduction

The importance of mastering agricultural practices for growth, development, and the transition from traditional society to increasingly advanced stages of society is highlighted by Xenophon when he declared that, agriculture is the mother of all arts, when it is well managed, all other arts flourish; but when it is neglected, all other arts decline, on land as well as at sea (quoted by Marein, 1993). This highlights the merits of family farms controlling agricultural activities within the framework of rural development.

Family farming is a set of issues to be understood and brought together in order to meet the challenges associated with it. In Eastern Cameroon, family farming is an economic challenge with more than 70% of poor people living in rural areas, and where the poverty index is more than double that in urban areas (SDN30). Despite this, it is the largest employer and the largest source of foreign currency, the rural sector being considered the preferred platform for boosting growth and reducing poverty (SDN30).

A social challenge with the rural exodus of young people to the cities, which leads to the aging of the rural population, the reduction of agricultural workers, and the devitalization of rural areas. A political challenge, with the lack of real structuring of producer organizations (POs) despite all the programs that intervene there, and the lack of representativeness of producer groups in decision-making bodies. An environmental challenge, given

June 30, 2025

that activities must integrate aspects of environmental preservation, natural resources, and the preservation of agricultural ecosystems (land, forest, water, biodiversity).

A comprehensive and coordinated approach to rural areas in their various social, economic, and environmental aspects, in order to capitalize on the complementarities between urban and rural areas and to develop the specific resources of rural areas (Lazarev, 2009). Rural development consists of maintaining a viable society in rural areas while reducing the importance of the attraction exerted by the city. It therefore involves a certain management of human development and the implementation of technological tools in order to improve knowledge and skills in an equitable and even sustainable manner.

In this sense, systems of supervision and support for producers that aim to modify productivity patterns and increase livelihoods in order to increase income, diversify activities, and improve the living conditions of the rural population must lead to a series of beneficial quantitative and qualitative changes occurring within the rural population; and including beneficial changes in thinking and work techniques (Peemans, 2011). Aiming to highlight the dynamics of support and supervision services in rural areas in order to better characterize their limits. This study provides a better understanding of support and supervision services within so-called family farming.

Material and Method

This study was conducted in Eastern Cameroon. For data collection, we conducted 21 interviews, including 7 with leaders of farmer organizations (POs), 7 with public and private agricultural advisory and extension services, and 7 with development support structures within the target population. A questionnaire was then randomly administered to leaders and members of 10 producer organizations (POs), among those identified at the delegations and advisory services in Eastern Cameroon. Another questionnaire was randomly administered to 50 agricultural producers not affiliated with POs for the purpose of conducting comparative analyses. Documents made available by POs and producer support services were also used in the literature search. As this study was qualitative, descriptive statistics were produced to describe the data. In addition, content analysis through systematic and objective procedures for describing the content of the statements allowed us to obtain indicators allowing the interpretation of the data.

Results and Discussion

I- Family farming, an emerging issue closely linked to the systems of supervision and support for producers in Eastern Cameroon

Family agropastoral farms (FAFs) are the expression of family farming. Family farming refers to one of the forms of organization of agricultural production, bringing together farms characterized by organic links between the family and the production unit and by the mobilization of family labor excluding permanent salaried employment (Bosc, 2014). In Eastern Cameroon, the FAF, although characterized by low levels of production and productivity, remains the pillar of production in the agricultural sector (ACEFA, 2018). They therefore ensure the means of subsistence but also the satisfaction of other basic needs. Indeed, in Eastern Cameroon, the FAFs play an important role in maintaining and creating jobs, local innovation, economic development of territories through the creation of local marketing channels, and the construction of collective identities.

I-1 Supervision and Support Systems: a driver of growth for family agropastoral farms in Eastern Cameroon

Agricultural supervision and support systems are comprehensive approaches that strengthen the capacities of farmers, and even their families, through monitoring their activities, situation analysis, decision-making support, and results evaluation. They take into account the technical, economic, social, and environmental aspects of their activities. Based on this analysis, we agree with Faure et al. (2011) on the importance of agricultural development systems as an important component in improving farm performance.

June 30, 2025

In our sample, for 84% of farmers not supported by advisory services and 71% supported by advisory services, agricultural development systems are essential in the modernization of agriculture. In addition, according to interviews with managers of farmer support services, producers need good supervision to improve their knowledge, optimize their operations and secure or facilitate the agricultural transition. In the same vein, Laplante (2015) states that the acquisition of knowledge and skills, which is done through intergenerational transmission or between neighbors, must benefit from permanent access to technical, economic or management advice and scientific advances in their field of activity. This helps strengthen farmers' skills and impact farms, working techniques, producers' incomes, as well as the entire agricultural chain built around speculation.

Moreover, the education, training, technology, and information provided by farmer support services are essential for improving operating conditions within the FAFs. This is evident from the testimonies of the producers we met, with some stating, "*Since our support with the council, our methods have changed a lot, and we are better informed*"; "*Since I've been supported, I manage my farm better and I now plan my budget, which allows me to prepare for the children's return to school without stressing myself out throughout the year.*" Upon analysis, support provided by an appropriate service can influence the entire socioeconomic environment of producers and thus improve living conditions in rural areas.

The research-consulting-producer relationships provided by the council allow producers not only to access agricultural innovations, but also to share field results and convey their impressions to the researcher. This is made possible by the consultation framework that maintains feedback on information, as is the case between Agricultural Research Institute for Development (IRAD) and Programme for the Improvement of Competitiveness of Family Agro-pastoral Farms (ACEFA). For example, the advances in seed conservation without the use of chemicals, established by IRAD in Cameroon and disseminated by public agricultural advisory services, and highlighted by some of the producers surveyed.

Family farming requires the mobilization of several factors, including financial capital, labor, and land as a basis for deployment. However, financial capital is still not easy to provide for FAFs, especially in the context of new investments, maintenance, and even strengthening of means of production. In this sense, FAFs need access to credit, which is not easy despite the existence of rural microfinance such as MUPECI, ACEP, MUFID which finance farmers. It emerges from farmers' testimony that some support organizations grant financing to producers under certain conditions, such as the National Participatory Development Program (PNDP). The National Fund for Rural Development (NFRD) grants repayable credits, with the possibility of donations in the event that the producer meets all repayment deadlines and makes a real profit over a specified period. ACEFA, for its part, provides competitive material financing to the FAFs, and 100% in orchard reconstruction and reforestation actions. In addition, it makes producers engaged in organic farming one of its priority areas of action. The Common Initiative Group (CIG) of Promoters of Agropastoral Productions (PAP) of Abong-Mbang and the CIG of Plumbers, Welders and Wheel Gluers of Bertoua (PSOCOBERT), both supervised by ACEFA, have seen their agricultural activity develop through advice and infrastructure financing, as they testify with great enthusiasm.

In Eastern Cameroon, agricultural development systems are a tool for growth in that they facilitate market reorganization, the construction of value chains, and even capacity building. This is the case, for example, in this testimony from producers in the Kadey department regarding the marketing of ginger in rural areas. Indeed, improved production techniques have led to overproduction and overabundance of ginger in local markets, and therefore lower prices. On the initiative of advisors, the POs have divided the given territories into four zones in order to distribute them, which has rebalanced market distribution and increased sales prices.

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June 30, 2025

As noted by most of the farmers interviewed, Eastern Cameroon is a region increasingly occupied by people from other regions who have their own way of life due to social changes. To maintain growth in rural areas, some services are supporting producers to combat food insecurity, inflation, and abundant, low-cost food at the expense of food security. Delegates from the ACAMP and FRATOB CIGs, as well as some producers not affiliated with the PO, affirm that diversification of farming in eastern Cameroon is encouraged by the Family Farm Advisory Service in light of local needs. Furthermore, new storage and marketing conditions are being established to improve the quality of FAF's products and therefore their competitiveness. This is the case of the National Participatory Development Program (PNDP), which is building sheds and warehouses throughout rural areas to allow farmers to better store and package their products.

I-2 The producer organization, an instrument for the professionalization of family agropastoral farms in Eastern Cameroon

Through Rambaud's (1976) analyses, the term peasant refers to three distinct elements of knowledge: the relationship between the individual and nature, the relationship between the social structure of labor, status, production function, and the distribution of authority within the community. Thus, in rural areas, the farmer is a cultivator or peasant, not a producer or agricultural operator. His production is carried out on small plots with rudimentary or poorly developed technology, a much more family-based workforce, and generally relies on the use of traditional inputs. His field, not the farm, generates little profit to distribute to the family, and he has difficulty accessing credit and training. In such conditions, it is difficult to give the farmer a real socio-professional status, since he remains attached to his identity as a peasant in view of his living and working conditions.

Indeed, the professionalization of FAFs is generally achieved through access to innovation, optimal decision-making, training, production techniques, and management within POs. Thus, coming together in a dynamic and structured PO not only allows for better supervision based on demands and knowledge building, but also through capacity building and the services provided. It is in this perspective that the promotion and enhancement of POs through supervision and support systems in Eastern Cameroon is in its essence a means of transforming the farmer's field into a farm, and building their socio-professional identity through professionalization. By building the identity of farmers through professionalization, *"farmers' organizations participate in the appropriation of the profession by farmers"* as the delegates of the CIG ACAMP and FRATOB testify, *"also since we have been supervised, third parties recognize us as professionals in our activities."* The CIG SALAM delegate also acknowledges that the support services have allowed them to better master their technical itineraries, better understand the opportunities of different productions, and optimize the management of their operations. Other producers say they have been able to more easily access economic information and organize themselves to improve their access to markets and other development factors.

POs also participate in the rationalization of FAFs. Rationality is defined as a choice situation in which a rational actor, faced with several alternative options, chooses the one they believe will lead to the best overall outcome (Meadwell, 2002). This vision of rationality, which corresponds to that of "homoeconomicus," is structured around five points: identifying the problem requiring a solution, establishing a list of all possible solutions, determining all the consequences associated with the solutions considered, conducting a comparative evaluation of the solutions, and selecting the optimal solution that maximizes the satisfaction of objectives (Quinet, 1994).

In our sample, for 41% of producers belonging to a PO, the latter allowed them to understand the challenges of their activity in the face of the various interactions that emerge and the importance of the group, and to better characterize an initial situation. Moreover, according to these producers, members of a PO who not only undergo capacity building and training, but also respond favorably to them, optimize individual and collective strategies.

Indeed, farmers whose primary activity is agriculture, regardless of the type of agriculture they practice, participate in one way or another in economic exchanges. To achieve this, in order to emancipate themselves,

June 30, 2025

they can no longer simply limit themselves to production for their primary function, but rather adopt a perspective of improved management alongside other sociocultural production functions. In this sense, the members of the CIG SALAM affirm that they are "*no longer viewed as people who have failed in life, but increasingly treated as leaders who are successful in their lives.*"

II- Family farming in the face of the fragility of supervision and support systems in the East region of Cameroon

In seeking to achieve their objectives, actors can understand the meaning they give to the information identifiable with a situation, or to the significant events they face. This makes it possible to understand a social world made up of the interweaving and sedimentation of social constructs of varying ages, varying degrees of stability or obsolescence. But also of natural or material elements whose meaning (but not necessarily their essence) is socially constructed (Loriol, 2012).

Thus, the structures of human association are determined essentially by shared ideas rather than by material forces, that is, they are defined by cultures rather than given by facts (Battistella, 2003). The practices, customs, and techniques of family farming are therefore structured by very diverse production methods. They can be peasant, traditional or intensified family farms, corporate, or collective. Family farming can therefore be considered as the interpenetration of the family and the farm, which implies that the family is capable of mobilizing the factors of production.

II-1 Human resources development: a shortcoming in agricultural supervision and support policies in Eastern Cameroon

While it is true that difficulties in securing credit (Desjeux, 2009) and bilateral agreements, which place extremely diverse farmers in competition with each other (Laplante, 2015), are among the constraints of agricultural supervision and support policies, the issue of human capital is another shortcoming that we will focus on.

Based on the definition of rural development used in this analysis, namely: the management of human development and the orientation of technological and institutional changes to improve inclusion, longevity, knowledge, and living standards in rural areas within a context of equity and sustainability, rural development has two fundamental dimensions: a qualitative dimension and a quantitative dimension.

The quantitative dimension is expressed by the term growth and refers to a process of wealth accumulation. From this perspective, rural development is analyzed as the increase in production which logically leads to a material increase. Thus, the main objectives that can be set in terms of rural development are dictated by the characteristics of the rural economy (Latortue, 1998). From this perspective, quantitative indicators include, among others, the increase in production or income, job creation, diversification of services, access to or structuring of markets.

The qualitative dimension in the context of rural development, which is the one that interests us in this analysis, is clearly visible through the distinction made by economists between development and growth. According to Perroux, growth is the sustained increase over one or more long periods of an indicator of dimension: for a nation, the net global product in real terms (Dictionary, 1990), which clearly refers to the quantitative dimension. On the other hand, development is the combination of mental and social changes that enable the nation to cumulatively and sustainably increase its global real product (Perroux, 1991). This definition highlights the qualitative dimension of rural development through indicators, human development and improvement of the living environment. We can therefore say with UNDP (2001) that human development is not limited, far from it, to the increase or decrease of national income. It aims to create an environment in which individuals can fully develop their potential and lead productive and creative lives, in accordance with their needs and interests. The true wealth of nations is their people. The role of development is therefore to expand the possibilities for everyone to choose the life that suits them. This concept thus goes far beyond that of economic growth.

June 30, 2025

Human capital or human resources development is a fundamental component of development, in this sense, Mandela (2007) declares "education is the most powerful weapon to change the world". In our sample, nearly 53% of respondents have a primary level of education, while nearly 11% have no education at all. In addition, people with a secondary level of education are more likely to be in the first cycle. Also, in our sample, the social categories with the best returns on their farms are those with a secondary or higher level of education and those with training in agriculture. Moreover, according to the development support agents surveyed, farmers with the most education or training in agriculture easily assimilate management and decision-making tools, generally adopt innovations first than others, and more easily develop interactions of all kinds in their environment. Regardless of the type of agricultural technology delivery system or the associated incentives, the quality of human capital is fundamental. According to some supervisors interviewed, farmers with low levels of education and training in agriculture have the highest failure rate when evaluating activities, monitoring technical itineraries, and when characterizing an initial situation with medium- and long-term development objectives. Furthermore, this type of farmer spends much more time on client follow-up portfolios than others, and are also, for the most part, the least dynamic within the POs.

This clearly demonstrates the importance of the human capital or component in public policies and development strategies as fundamental. Indeed, from a long-term development perspective in the context of family farming, it is not the development of agriculture but that of the farmer that will influence every aspect of their lives. However, the analysis of activity reports in the programs considered in this study, such as that of ACEFA phase 2, shows that less than 3% of their budget is actually devoted to the training of human capital (ACEFA, 2018). It is not wrong that in the industrial sector one of the factors of development is "skilled workers". The same is true in family farming which tends to become more professional. As a result, the main production factor for agricultural development within the FAF should no longer be perceived through indicators of arable land, credits, or increase in farm space, but first by the quality of human capital and their knowledge which influence their capacity for innovation and mobilization. Because, the fragility of the human capital of the FAF in the current configurations of family farming are serious obstacles to overcome for their development.

II-2 Producer organizations: a major asset, paralyzing family farming in Eastern Cameroon

Farmer organizations or producer organizations in rural areas are not a new reality. However, the dynamics of producer organizations as structured today were driven in Cameroon in the early 1990s following structural reforms in its economy. Despite its shortcomings, farmer organizations are a development asset for family farming, especially since, in a business strategy, a producer should seek to maximize their real income by optimizing their means of production. This is not the case in the sample surveyed.

Among the respondents who do not belong to farmer organizations, 53% consider farmer organizations to be an instrument of domination and exploitation of some over others. 37% were members of a farmer organization but left due to inertia or poor governance. 30% do not know what a PO is for, 31% have had bad experiences with POs, and 67% say POs are used to organize themselves to receive in-kind and/or cash support.

Among those surveyed who are members of POs, 33% are ready to leave their PO, 64% joined the PO to obtain funding from external aid, 31% joined because a relative asked them to form a group, and 11% decided to join a PO to pool their efforts.

Analysis reveals that producers are unaware of the advantages or benefits of a PO. They are poorly informed and aware of the purpose of POs. Most of them are wait-and-see and do not understand the meaning of pooling efforts. The attractiveness of POs today lies in the professionalization of FAFs through the modulation of a certain number of behaviors. CIGs and cooperatives are being analyzed as small, family-based agri-food companies with reduced and simplified taxation, which should allow the FAF to set up production units through the coordination and mobilization of resources in the medium and long term. Indeed, just as banking institutions have microfinance institutions alongside them, agribusiness companies should see the development of a veritable network of "mini-agribusiness" establishments made up of Professional Agropastoral Organizations (PAO).

June 30, 2025

However, the main concern of POs is not their training, but the financing of their activities (a behavior rooted in the values of the structural adjustment program period). They lack the fundamental managerial skills needed for development. Moreover, during the surveys, we observed funded infrastructure that had been abandoned by POs. Some advisory and development service agents also highlighted the abandonment of certain sheds, farms, and buildings due to poor management, or of certain defective machinery abandoned due to lack of monitoring. Indeed, the FAFs do not integrate POs as an efficient resource for managing their farms. Farmers seek to appropriate as much equipment and an ever-increasing area of land as possible, like a form of heritage devoid of the notion of capital or investment. This generally results in the dissolution of the group once the original goal is achieved, or its disintegration when it is slow to materialize. Because they are created without intelligible objectives, which makes them dependent and passive.

Conclusion

Rural development in Eastern Cameroon still relies heavily on family farming. This is why support services for producers are important in this endeavor. When well-designed, they greatly contribute to modernizing agriculture as a whole and to strengthening farmers' capacities. What is lacking in development strategies and farmer-led approaches is the importance given to human capital. Indeed, the limited investment in training by agricultural development systems and technologies, and the glaring lack of interest among rural producers in personal training and mutualization, paralyze producer organizations, which should currently be seen as an added value.

Based on the above analyses, it is important for both public authorities and their partners, as well as for producers, to make training, continuing education, and awareness-raising a fundamental component of their entire activity policy. Indeed, the analysis shows that human capital is a definite investment both for the capitalization of knowledge and the sustainability of other investments in agriculture.

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